

Application of Machine Learning (ML); a tool for teaching and future research in undergraduate chemistry laboratory experiment ‘Extent of miscibility of the Phenol-Water system’

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This paper demonstrates how machine learning methods can replace conventional approaches to fitting data measured in chemistry experiments, especially those which are conducted at the undergraduate level. As a case study, raw data collected from a Phenol-water experiment is used to outline the methodology needed to arrive at the best fit curve. Code snippets are provided and explained in detail and metrics from different models are tabulated and compared. The model with the best performing metrics is then chosen as the representative fit.

Keywords: Phenol-water system, miscibility, machine learning (ML), best fit.

Introduction

The extent of miscibility study of the Phenol-Water system (partially miscible liquids)¹ is a well-studied laboratory experiment for undergraduate physical chemistry students in most of the universities. The extent of miscibility is determined by temperature. The reversed U-shaped curve (Fig. 1) can be viewed

Fig. 1. Solubility curve of Phenol-Water system.

as made up of two halves. The left being the solubility curve of Phenol in Water and the other the solubility Water in Phenol. Both the curves meet at 66°C temperature, where the solutions is saturated (i.e. Water in Phenol and Phenol in Water, have the same composition).

The thermodynamic forces driving the solubility nature of the Phenol-Water system shows that the enthalpy of solution (ΔH_s) in the saturated solution is positive i.e. that the system absorbs heat and so solubility increases with increase in temperature which supports the Le Châtelier's Principle. More meticulously, one student can determine whether solubility of the minor component increases or decreases with temperature with the help of the equation -

$$\frac{d \ln sf_2}{dT_s} = \frac{\Delta H_s}{RT_s^2} \quad (i)$$

where 's' is the solubility expressed in mole fraction units, 'f₂' is the corresponding activity coefficient and 'T_s' is the temperature at which the solution is saturated.

The line of the reversed U-shaped curve (commonly called as Umbrella curve) maps the variation in composition of saturated solutions (phenol in water and water in phenol) with the change in temperature¹. The area to the left of the curve represents unsaturated solutions of phenol in water and the area to the right represents unsaturated solutions of water in phenol, while the

area above the curve represents solutions of phenol and water that are fully miscible in all proportions.

But inside the curve, which is beyond the saturation limits of water in phenol and phenol in water, the phenomenon is something different. In this region, the system divides into two co-existent phases, the upper phase being the saturated solution of phenol-in-water and the lower phase is the reverse. The inquisitive finding of these phases is - for a fixed temperature their composition remain fixed even though the total amounts of phenol and water composing them may vary.

Undergraduate students often face difficulties in handling data born out of laboratory experiments. Guessing the nature of the graph by merely observing its visual characteristics leads to an imprecise model and not the best fit. The teaching strategy should, therefore, include tools and techniques which enable students to address such problems. These tools would also come handy for students in undertaking future research.

Computer programming is taught in the curriculum of undergraduate students in chemistry. However machine learning (ML) methods are not usually a part of the programming course². So, the curriculum one can incorporate this method in analyzing data obtained from empirical findings³.

Objective

The objective of this paper is to demonstrate how methods in *statistical machine learning*⁴ can be applied to the data⁵ obtained from a laboratory experiment of the Phenol-Water system. This experiment is performed to study a phenomenon known as liquid-liquid phase equilibrium^{6,7,8} and is an example of partially miscible liquids. The mutual *solubility temperature* of the system is measured experimentally at various *mass%* of phenol and the ensuing graph - maps the relationship between the two.

Data source

The following set of data points were collected as part of the above experiment conducted in a laboratory by the author in Hans Raj College, Delhi. 'x' represents *Mass% of Phenol* while 'y' stands for *Miscibility Temperature*.

X	70	67	64.49	59.85	57.77	55.83
y	37.5	44.8	49.6	56.8	59.0	62.1
X	54.02	46.47	40.77	36.32	32.74	27.36
y	62.8	65.1	65.5	66	65.3	64.8
X	23.49	18.32	15.01	12.71	10.67	10.67
y	63.9	61	56.5	51.3	42.9	

```
Set_X = [70, 67, 64.49, 59.85, 57.77, 55.83, 54.02, 46.47, 40.77, 36.32, 32.74, 27.36, 23.49, 18.32, 15.01, 12.71, 10.67]
Set_y = [37.5, 44.8, 49.6, 56.8, 59.0, 62.1, 62.8, 65.1, 65.5, 66, 65.3, 64.8, 63.9, 61, 56.5, 51.3, 42.9]
```

Here is a visualization of the dataset in graph (Fig. 2):

Fig. 2. Solubility curve of Phenol-Water system (Dataset -1).

Methodology

The *Python* programming language will be used to demonstrate how *Machine Learning (ML)* can fit data points. The libraries used are listed below:

1. *Matplotlib* will be used for plotting and visualization.
2. *NumPy* is a standard library used to perform high speed computation on multidimensional data.
3. *Scikit learn* contains a battery of routines needed to train and test a variety of ML models.
4. *Pandas* is a data analytics and manipulation library.

The following ML models will be run on this data to estimate the best fit:

1. *Linear Regression*⁸ will first be used to fit a *straight line*
2. *Polynomial Regression*⁹ with *degree 2* will subsequently be applied to fit a *parabola*
3. *Polynomial Regression with degree 3* will finally be run to map a *cubic curve*

Each model run will be evaluated against 2 error metrics:

1. *MSE (Mean Square Error)*¹⁰ Closer this is to 0, better is the fit
2. *R² (Coefficient of Determination)*¹¹ Closer this is to 1, better is the fit

Applying machine learning

1. Split data for training and testing
 - a. The *train_test_split* method in *sklearn* accepts X and y and then shuffles and splits the data into 2 subsets: A *training* and a *testing* set
 - b. The split ratio is governed by the *test_size* parameter which in this case is 0.33. Since the dataset has 17 entries, 0.33 of 17 rounded up is 6 is used for testing and 11 is used for training

```
# Shuffle data points
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.33,
                                                    random_state=42)
```


Fig. 3. Solubility curve of Phenol-Water system; training data vs. testing data (Dataset -1).

2. Training data using Linear Regression

```
# Create linear regression object  
regr = linear_model.LinearRegression()  
  
# Train the model using the training set  
regr.fit(X_train, y_train)
```

3. Inspect model weights

```
# The coefficients  
print('Coefficients: \n', regr.coef_)  
print('Intercept: \n', regr.intercept_)
```

```
Coefficients:  
[0.0299661]  
Intercept:  
58.59707132350741
```

4. Print error metrics

```
from sklearn.metrics import mean_squared_error, r2_score  
  
print('Mean squared error: %.2f'  
      % mean_squared_error(y_test, regr.predict(X_test)))  
  
# The coefficient of determination: 1 is perfect prediction  
print('Coefficient of determination: %.2f'  
      % r2_score(y_test, regr.predict(X_test)))
```

```
Mean squared error: 147.59  
Coefficient of determination: -0.63
```

5. Plot linear fit over dataset

Fig. 4. Liner regression of dataset.

6. Preparing data for Polynomial Regression

- a. Data needs to be transformed before it can be used for training
- b. For instance, in the case of a linear fit, there is only 1 feature X and a bias term
- c. For a quadratic, 2 features, X , X^2 and a bias term
- d. For a cubic, 3 features, X , X^2 , X^3 and a bias term
- e. The *Polynomial Features* class in *sklearn* helps in achieving this

```
from sklearn.preprocessing import PolynomialFeatures
poly_reg = PolynomialFeatures(degree=2)
X_poly = poly_reg.fit_transform(X_train)

print(X_poly)
```

```
[[1.0000000e+00 4.0770000e+01 1.6621929e+03]
 [1.0000000e+00 1.8320000e+01 3.3562240e+02]
 [1.0000000e+00 6.4490000e+01 4.1589601e+03]
 [1.0000000e+00 3.6320000e+01 1.3191424e+03]
 [1.0000000e+00 1.0670000e+01 1.1384890e+02]
 [1.0000000e+00 5.7770000e+01 3.3373729e+03]]
```

7. Training data using Polynomial Regression

```
regr.fit(X_poly, y_train)
```

8. Plot Quadratic fit over Dataset

Fig. 5. Plot Quadratic fit over Dataset.

9. Repeat process for Cubic fit

Fig. 6. Plot of Cubic regression.

Result

Comparison of models

Error metric	<i>Linear</i>	<i>Quadratic</i>	<i>Cubic</i>
<i>MSE</i>	147.59	8.15	23.13
R^2	-0.63	0.91	0.75

The Quadratic curve demonstrates the best performance both in terms of a low MSE as well as the highest R^2 closest to 1. The Model has the following weights:

```
print('Coefficients: \n', regr.coef_)
print('Intercept: \n', regr.intercept_)
```

Coefficients:

```
[ 0.          2.0552255 -0.0264083]
```

Intercept:

```
27.60382771068329
```

Conclusion

The paper shows how it is advisable to use proper ML methods rather than arbitrary techniques to identify the best fit curve on experimental data. In undergraduate settings, it has been observed that students will choose a parabola by merely looking at the data plot. They do not verify whether the chosen curve yields the least error. This paper methodically establishes the correct approach which needs to be employed in place of educated guess work. It can be verified that the chosen model aligns consistently with its theory. The techniques described can be extended to explore relationship in any new experimental research whose outcome is not known beforehand.

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Appendix (Complete code snippet)

```
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import numpy as np
from sklearn import linear_model
import pandas as pd
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.linear_model import LinearRegression
from sklearn.preprocessing import PolynomialFeatures

# Utility function which plots best fit curve over original dataset
def visualize_curve_fit(X, y, reg, poly_transform):
    plt.scatter(X, y, color='red')
    plt.plot(X, reg.predict(poly_transform.fit_transform(X)), color='blue')
    plt.title('Phenol Curve Fit')
    plt.xlabel('Mass')
    plt.ylabel('Temp')
    plt.show()
    return

# Main method which tries to fit curve of given degree on the dataset
def phenol_experiments(X, y, degree=2):

    # Shuffle and Split the dataset into training and testing sets
    X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.33,
    random_state=42)

    # Plot what the training dataset looks like
    plt.scatter(X_train, y_train, color='red')
    plt.title('Training Data')
```

```

plt.xlabel('Mass')
plt.ylabel('Temp')
plt.show()

# Plot what the test dataset looks like
plt.scatter(X_test, y_test, color='blue')
plt.title('Testing Data')
plt.xlabel('Mass')
plt.ylabel('Temp')
plt.show()

# Transform the training data into polynomial features
# e.g. linear data set [x] -> [1, x]
# e.g. quadratic data set [x] -> [1, x, x*x]
# e.g. cubic data set [x] -> [1, x, x*x, x*x*x]
poly_transform = PolynomialFeatures(degree)
X_poly = poly_transform.fit_transform(X_train)

# Print out the transformed Dataset
print(X_poly)

# Now, fit the training data into a Linear Regression model
reg = LinearRegression()
reg.fit(X_poly, y_train)

# Print out the model parameters
print('Coefficients: \n', reg.coef_)
print('Intercept: \n', reg.intercept_)

# Print out error scores
print('Mean squared error: %.2f'
      % mean_squared_error(y_test, reg.predict(poly_transform.
->fit_transform(X_test))))

# The coefficient of determination: 1 is perfect prediction
print('Coefficient of determination: %.2f'
      % r2_score(y_test, reg.predict(poly_transform.fit_transform(X_test))))

# Visualize the model over the entire dataset
visualize_curve_fit(X,y,reg, poly_transform)

return reg

```


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